

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE GOAL OF THE EVIL EMPIRE IS TO DESTROY UKRAINE

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Abstract

Empires are an extraordinary phenomenon in the history of mankind. The study of empires requires scientific understanding, thoughtful comparison and deep analysis. Such way of studding the comparative approach of the problem has arisen that will help us understand the nature of the emergence and disappearance of imperial formations, find answers to difficult questions: how empires grew, for what reasons some of them were powerful and others weak, why some empires disappeared and others flourished. Is there a connection between the instability of power, coups and the death of empires? And finally, what are the consequences for world development of the disappearance of imperial formations. Among the reasons for the demise of empires, researchers single out political and economic problems, social and cultural issues, and environmental challenges.

The author of the article tries to explain how the Moscow Empire was formed, how the Russian Empire manages to survive despite a number of dangerous challenges. The idea of revival and development of the empire thanks to the support of former vassals who were part of the imperial formation was substantiated by the author of the article on the example of the history of the Russian Empire. This phenomenon reminds us of the Scandinavian syndrome, when victims begin to protect and save their tormentor, who has done them irreparable evil.

So, the article examines the factors that support and revive imperial formations, and also makes cautious assumptions about the future scenarios of the development of events surrounding the current situation.

Keywords: *Ukraine, evil empiere, humanity, nationalism, phenomenon*

Formulation of the problem

The concept of empire comes from *Latin*. *Imperium* means command, supreme power, management of a certain territory by one person – the monarch. The empire is one of the historical forms of state-political formation. In nowadays this term was defined as individual sovereignty over numerous and dispersed political societies. The British historian, specialist in the history of Russia *Dominik Lieven* (2000) proposed to define the empire as a state with a clearly demarcated territory exercising sovereignty over its subjects, who are under its direct administrative supervision at various (*Mark R. Beissinger, 2015*).

The term "empire" has caused much controversy and has been applied to many different political entities. Oxford University professor *John Darwin* (2008) spoke of the existence of an unofficial empire as the highest form of imperialism. According to his definition, empires are systems of influence or rule in which ethnic, cultural, or ecological boundaries overlapped or were ignored. It should be noted that the term "empire" refers primarily to the central state of such entities, which unites others and exercises political control over a large territory containing many diverse population groups.

We usually speak about the empire as a whole. But since the empires are quite large, they are often divided into smaller, more manageable political units, which are called provinces, and in Soviet Russia – the union of republics.

Comparing different empires, it is possible to find commonalities and differences in their development. Analysts offer for consideration several vivid examples of former and existing empires, tracing their path from birth to collapse. Thus, the famous British academic *John Hutchinson* in his study "Warfare, Imperial Collapse, and the Mass Creation of Nation States Get access Arrow" (*Sarkees, M. R., Wayman, F. W., and Singer, J. D, 1998*) mentions the Persian Achaemenid Empire under the leadership of Cyrus the Great, the Maurya Empire in India, the Roman Republic, which was founded in the sixth century BC, and others. According to the scientist, empires appear for various reasons. Thus, the Persian Achaemenid Empire was built mainly through military conquests. The Mauryan Empire in India used a combination of political sabotage and religious conversion to expand its rule. The Roman invaders, creating an empire, differed in that they did not aim for the final conquest of the territory. And after victory, Rome usually offered some level of citizenship to foreigners in exchange for loyalty.

Let's return to Eurasia, where the Muscovite empire was formed. In fact, all the components of its formation were borrowed from other historical eras and cultures: seizing territories, harsh exploitation of peoples and resources, bribery, destruction of resistance, blackmail, demonstration of force, assimilation of conquered peoples, etc. That Russian empire existed for seven centuries and, despite world cataclysms, destruc-

tion and disintegration, survived again in a new capacity. The kingdom of Moksel grew especially actively territorially during the time of tsar Peter the First – the tsar of "All russia", who declared himself the All-russian Emperor in 1721.

The territorial expansion of the empire began in 1690 with the Azov campaigns against the Ottoman Empire, the first of which, with the attack on the Turkish fortress of Azov in 1695, failed. At the same time, the existence of the Russian Empire as a state entity ended in 1917 with the proclamation of the Russian Republic on September 1, 1917. The primary causes of the collapse of the empire were the First World War and the aggravation of national disputes between national minorities, to which we will add the economic factor – the development of productive forces.

The fall of empires is caused by a number of objective and subjective factors. The first sign is the inability of the central state to rule. This happens if the central state ceases to exist or its power has weakened, the captured territories have left the control of the central government, declaring their own independence, etc. Researchers try to explain the collapse of empires with the following reasons. First of all, economic, although the author of the article believes that the root cause of this phenomenon is rather military redistribution of territories between invaders. We will add political and social reasons to the above. It is desirable to take into account the fact that military, economic and political often occur simultaneously, that is, they act as a single pool. Among other reasons, as mentioned, social, cultural and environmental problems etc. are also singled out.

Analysis of previous research and publications

Nationalism is considered the traditionally a source the emergence of new states after the fall of empires. *M. Sarkees, F. Wayman, D. Singer wrote about this (Sarkees, M.R., Wayman, F.W., Singer, J.D. 1998)*. In our opinion, *this question can be controversial*, since states appear not only as a result of the strengthening of national self-awareness of society. And the results of two World Wars prove it. So, secondly, the factor of nationalism is far from decisive in the process of nation-building and state-building. In the 20th-21st centuries a number of new national formations appear relatively quickly as a result of clashes of interests of the world's leading powers. Thus, as a result of the Second World War, three dozen new states appeared on the world map, which, seeking international protection, quickly joined the ranks of the United Nations. The air of freedom in the post-war times covered almost all the peoples subject to the metropolises in Europe, Asia, the Middle East, and the African continent.

The appearance of a number of new/old state entities characterizes a new era of the end of the confrontation in the Cold War, when with the collapse of the USSR, 15 countries appeared on its territory – the former Soviet republics of Central and Eastern Europe, as well as Central Asia. Researcher *M. Sarkis* calculated that the number of participants in the interstate order increased from 23 to 181 countries in 1816-1995 (*M. Sarkis*) At the same time, we should note that Western

analysts, as a rule, are not delighted with the new emergence of newly formed states and warn that a significant number of new subjects/objects of international relations was the challenges portends of the new wars. They consider this factor a security challenge to global and regional stability. At the same time, let's recall how the world's analytical "progressive" Beaumont (!) was met negative emergence of an independent but nuclear Ukraine (*Ambassador Miller 1993-1996, 2023*). So, the author examines the factors that support and revive imperial formations. Also professor makes cautious assumptions about the future scenarios of the development of events surrounding the current situation.

Introductory remarks

The Moscow Empire continued to expand during the past centuries, as the overseas empires of national states - Great Britain, France, Spain, Portugal, the Netherlands, Belgium, as well as Japan against the background of a number of world cataclysms. Some empires collapsed in the 20th century, but others arose or were restored on new foundations. *The Moscow Empire after 1917 was saved by the creation of the Soviet Union*. So USSR was strengthened by the victory over Germany in 1945 and received a ring of puppet states in Eastern and Central Europe. At the same time, although European maritime empires formally disintegrated in the decade after 1945, international events demonstrated the existence of so-called informal empires in which former colonial territories were subordinated to global institutions dominated by the United States and its Western allies. The Russian creation of post-war times can also be attributed to informal empires, which left signs of imperial rule in the territories included in its structure, hiding behind the artificially imposed ideology of building socialism/communism. (*Alfred J. Rieber, 2015*). In the result of studying a number of wars and their consequences, scientists came to the conclusion that it is impossible to explain the collapse of the empire and the emergence of national states only by military factors – threats and wars. In the global world, other mechanisms of influence on the stability of empires are economic factors and the role of first power persons.

Methodology of writing an article

The scientific method used to study the issue of empires is a *systematic approach*, namely the identification among them of the most characteristic groups that are similar in their characteristics. The first group includes the so-called agrarian empires of the Romanov, Habsburg, and Ottoman empires, which over the centuries absorbed various territories, including independent already formed pro-state entities. Starting from the seventeenth century, they periodically fought on their disputed border lands, forming an ethnically mixed population on the demarcation lines, which in the future gave rise to new wars and confrontations for the ownership of undivided territories. The second group included overseas empires in America, Africa, and Asia, which were defined as nation-empires. Unlike agrarian ones, they were mainly maritime, and non-European and non-Christian population was under their rule. Large-scale colonial expansion was the impetus for the huge industrial and communication revolutions

of the 19th century. Even the Chinese Empire was threatened with division due to the conspiracy of European powers and Japan, which also made its claims to the Chinese Empire (*Alfred J. Rieber, 2015*).

The Soviet empire, which survived the revolution and civil war, was preserved by Bolshevik Russia on the former territory of the Romanov Empire, although it lost Finland, the Baltic and Polish territories. Officially, it was a federation of equal national republics of the Russian, Belarusian, Ukrainian, and Transcaucasian peoples, but in fact it was a Russian fiefdom that openly and impunitously exploited the population of the renewed empire. All power structures and state institutions were dominated by Russians, and in the cultural and educational space – history, culture and language of Russians. After the Second World War, the power of this empire spread to Eastern and Central Europe, and the "socialist camp" was formed from the satellite states where the Soviet troops were stationed. *US President Ronald Reagan* called Russia an *evil empire* (*Martin, T., 2000*).

The process of the existence of empires in the scientific environment is explained by a number of theories, most of which gravitate towards realism and, in particular, the theory of imperialism. The main explanations of imperialist imperialism can be grouped into three general categories. *Metrocentric theories* focus on the dispositions or internal characteristics of imperial states. For example, *John A. Hobson* (1902) justified the motivation of foreign expansion by the need for advanced capitalist countries to export their surplus capital. This topic was also the basis of the work of the Soviet leader "Imperialism: the highest stage of capitalism", published in 1917. Later, neo-Marxists argued that the military-industrial complex and other features of capitalist states actually create the need for capital. In order to build up capital, they introduce colonial and neo-colonial relations with developing regions in order to extract the wealth they have accumulated. The state of relations within the colonial states is confirmed by *pericentric theories*, draw attention to the forces that involve the imperialists in a hierarchical relationship with the world (*Harry Magdoff, 1998*). At the same time, *metrocentric theories* focus on explaining the reasons for imperialist countries' desire for expansion (*Gallagher, John and Robinson, Ronald, 1953*). According to the authors, the policy of the imperialist countries towards the colonies changed depending on the expected results and conditions on the periphery. Where peripheral states had stable regimes and effective collaborators, imperialists could rule indirectly through informal empires.

Only where peripheral societies were politically unstable or lacked elites ready to protect their interests were metropolises forced to create formal empires and rule them directly. In the Russian Empire, which later became the Soviet Union, such republics as Tatarstan, Ingushetia, Bashkortostan, etc., where there were stable regimes and worked for the center - Muscovy - effective collaborators, the imperialists in power could rule indirectly through informal empires. In contrast to backward Russian regions, the so-called "gray zone", such as the Yamalo-Nenets district, Komi, Kalmykia,

Yakutia, etc., the central government of Moscow created a special system of institutions, appointing its people from the central apparatus to managerial positions, and later through an officially appointed representative of the president, endowed with the widest powers in the district, where such a center directly governed the "gray zone". Another group of theories, called *systemic theories of imperialism*, are mainly descendants and followers of realist theories of international relations, and they focus on the study of the survival process of large competing states. The struggle for survival and influence creates an ever-widening space of competition between great powers, prompting metropolises to seize territories to increase their resources, using peripheral territories to maintain an effective balance of power. A classic example of imperialism driven by systemic competition was the so-called "race for Africa" at the end of the 19th century. Such researchers of imperialism as *Hobson, Gallagher and Robinson* paid attention to the theory of systemic competition, namely to the peripheral causes of imperialism. The following studies of the development of empires are distinguished by a synergistic approach, which combined all the theoretical concepts listed above to explain the essence of imperialism.

The combination of military and nationalist aspirations of each of the empires was different, depending on the capabilities, personal characteristics, as well as on the time and place of their existence. However, all empires have the following in common. Imperial stability was based, and what we see today, based on a combination of conquest, ideological legitimization, coercion and co-optation of minority elites. The control schemes used were indirect rule through collaborationists based on a divide-and-conquer strategy. The latter meant differentiation in the army, in which certain ethnic groups of the central state were selected as "military races", as well as a specific demographic policy, in which the colonization of the dominant ethnic group of the invading central state was used to control the indigenous population. And today, from front-line reports, we observe the differentiation in the Russian army, the confrontation between ordinary soldiers of "peripheral" and non-ethnic origins and officers of the central headquarters. We are observing the colonization, assimilation and russification of the native Ukrainian local population. It is possible to draw a number of coincidental parallels, comparing the events in Ukraine, which is fighting against the invader, and the theoretical positions and opinions of well-known analysts and scientists.

According to *Randall Collins (2012)*, war is a central event for the legitimacy of states, and geopolitical principles govern the ethnic absorption or fragmentation of a country. States, the analyst writes, are mobile geographical entities that are in military competition with each other. All other things being equal, states that have an advantage in size and resources over their competitors will tend to expand territorially. As they expand, such states become overextended, resource-poor, and at risk of fragmentation as they create multiple enemies on their borders. Moreover, the cumulative processes of competing imperial expansions bring periodic

confluence with large-scale arms races and wars that generate the highest levels of hatred and rage.

The American researcher *R. Collins*, having studied the Balkan crisis, identified three stages in its development and proposed a three-stage model of activation of national groups seeking freedom. In this model, we may be interested in the third stage, which consists in the phase of mobilization of people, in which the sense of opportunities created as a result of the crisis gives rise to a surge of intense emotions, new symbols and concepts of identity.

Complementing Collins, *Andreas Wimmer* argues that nationalist mobilization is the driving force in all cases of imperial collapse, and that nationalist movements have been central to the transformation of the international system over the past two hundred years. The researcher's argument rests in part on statistical data, which he combines with detailed historical analysis. With few exceptions, nationalist organizations (defined as official institutions claiming to represent the population or part of a territory) preceded and were responsible for both the fall of empire and the transition to national sovereignty (*Andreas Wimmer*, 2013).

The strength of nationalist movements is directly related to the transition from empire to nation-state. Nationalist wars of liberation fought in other parts of the empire (the "diffusion of nationalism effect") increased the likelihood of nation-states, and the more territories that could be separated to form nation-states, the more likely that the remaining territories would follow suit.

Other important factors may be the weak international position of the imperial center, the prior creation of nation-states in the neighborhood but outside the imperial territories, and finally the wars of the great powers fought within the empire itself. Let us recall the two Chechen wars of Russia, or the war of Russia against Georgia, as well as the war of Russia against Ukraine. Internal wars, as *Giers and Wimmer* recognize, are a particularly influential factor in shaking empires (*Hiers and Wimmer*, 2013).

Although in the Second World War, the USSR and the USA acted as allies and jointly ensured the victory of the states of the anti-Hitler coalition, however, before the end of the war, misunderstandings and contradictions began to arise between them, which was caused by the desire to take over most of the world. In particular, the desire of the USSR, contrary to the Atlantic Charter, to establish its hegemony in Europe and some Asian regions. The Soviet leadership, inspired by the victory over fascism, under the guise of renewed theories about socialist construction led by totalitarian communist regimes, began actively promoting the unifying idea of creating a single integration space under its Moscow leadership. Thus, it tried to implement the plan to return the imperialist foundations of the former Russian Empire to the Soviet Union.

Finally, the Cold War ended with the collapse of the USSR in 1991, and its consequences beyond the collapse of the USSR were the redistribution of spheres of influence in favor of NATO, the emergence of new independent states, the deterioration of the foreign policy position of the center of the empire – the Russian Federation, the emergence of the United States as the

hegemon of world economic and political development, which willingly helped newly established states. The consequences of the emergence of new states, often artificially separated from integral territories with an ethnically mixed population, are not a positive phenomenon both for individual stable communities and for the world as a whole. Often, the appearance of new objects / subjects of international relations causes devastating consequences of the large-scale entry of such states into the interstate system of a stable space. Thus, the third wave of the collapse of empires is connected with the liquidation of the Soviet Union and the system of "socialism".

Taking into account the above, as well as observing signs of the formation of new, in particular, totalitarian unions in the era of global interdependence, we do not exclude the possibility of the appearance of new/old empires in a new capacity.

In connection with this, the question arises: what was the role of the "outlying lands" of the imperial Russian space, in particular Ukraine?

Conclusions and summary

Turning to recent historical events, let us recall that the now independent states - the former Soviet republics - the former outskirts of the Russian Empire played an almost decisive role in those events. *It was they who helped to preserve the Russian Empire from 1917*, adopting the rules of the imperial game of "subjugate and rule", without causing the corresponding resistance of the invader, splitting on two sides of the barricade, when the Russian bandit troops of General Muravyov looted Kyiv and drowned other territories of Ukraine in blood.

A similar task to save Russia was implemented by the leadership of the Ukrainian republic after the Second World War. Happy with the gift that the bloodthirsty leader gave the Ukrainian SSR a seat in the United Nations (1945), Ukraine actively voted for all Moscow's decisions already from the "high" podium of the world international "peacekeeping" organization of the UN. At that time, as well as at the beginning of the last century, until the end of the 1950s, "ideologically" separated Ukrainian soldiers in forest shelters gave their unique and unique lives for the freedom and future of independent Ukraine with the last words on their lips: Glory to Ukraine!

Wasn't a similar scenario played out already in our time – the time of existence of Ukraine, which is officially recognized by the world as a legal entity? Let's recall the years 1990-1991, during the collapse of the Soviet Union, all friends of Russia – "fraternal republics" scattered, frightened by the events of the Moscow coup of the GKChP.

Who saved Muscovy-Russia, trembling in agony, from final disintegration?

So, *Ukrainian brothers* were the saviors and Ukrainian government, Ukrainian president who was elected by the Ukrainian people, who created a new union with Moscow – *the Commonwealth of Independent States*. So Ukraine saved a new satrapy, a new empire from destruction. An empire that was well prepared for a war against us, aimed at our destruction.

Thus, *Prof. Chekalenko Liudmyla D. for the first time in historical and political dimensions revealed the phenomenon of "saving" the Russian empire.*

The revival of the Muscovite empire - the conqueror, exterminator and exploiter, assimilator of peoples and cultures - was repeatedly carried out by its vassals - conquered peoples, including Ukrainians. This phenomenon reminds us of the Scandinavian syndrome, when victims begin to protect and save their tormentor, who committed irreparable evil and inflicted severe injuries on them.

How Russia thanked it's savior - Ukraine – we see today! Russia thanked hundreds of human victims, the destruction of cities and villages, the destruction of everything Ukrainian.

Russia's goal is to eliminate Ukraine

Russia, still being a Russian and Soviet empire, never abandoned the idea of seizing Ukrainian lands. During the periods when it was weak, it did not dare to take such a step, because Ukraine was strong, and according to some signs, even stronger than its neighbor. Russia tried to implement territorial encroachments in Crimea, Sevastopol, the island of Kosa Tuzla, etc. The reasons for Russian interest in the absorption of Ukraine have already been described and researched more than once in the publications of the author of this article (*Chekalenko Liudmyla D., 2016*).

Russia prepared to invasion very carefully. The first step of the hot war in February 2022 was the unexpected march of Russian troops - paratroopers from the Kyiv Sea of the Vyshgorod district to the capital of Ukraine Kyiv.

The Russian war strategy was developed by all analytical centers in Moscow in advance, as soon as Ukraine announced its irreversible course towards Europe, European integration and NATO. During the period of "independence", the aggressor identified the weakest points in the Ukrainian defense, thoroughly studied the terrain and deployment points of the Ukrainian armed forces, and then struck on the night of February 23-24, 2022 – the day of the Soviet Army and Navy: the enemy has a tendency to tie their actions to some historical dates and numbers.

So, the well-thought-out, long-term, secretive work of the Russian invader, which was activated from the Ukrainian Maidans, continued for years in all directions: *political* (prolonging the time with legal recognition of Ukraine, with the signing of basic documents; pressure on the issue of nuclear weapons, the elimination of our defense and offensive potential, the destabilization of all administrative structures by the appointment of Russian officials to public positions, interference in internal affairs, the "appointment" of their presidents, etc.); *security* (advancement of the Russian military to the territory of Ukraine to create a fifth column, shipment of weapons, training of traitors, collection of tactical information, etc.); *economic* (non-repayment of debts, seizure of all Soviet real estate and property of the USSR, raising energy prices to an unattainable height, refusal of Ukrainian salt, metal, coal, transition to market prices for all components, etc.); *diplomatic* (refusal to distribute real estate of dip-

lomatic missions of the USSR, blocking Ukrainian international initiatives, hindering Ukraine's relations with other countries, etc.); *informational* (invasion of the information space of the USSR, the network of radio and TV frequencies, satellite-space communication, printed potential, etc.).

The corresponding work was carried out on the preparation to Russian fakes of world opinion, the history of the two countries and the USSR was distorted, Ukrainian textbooks on the history, international relations and foreign policy of Ukraine were banned. At the same time, large-scale anti-Ukrainian information work was carried out, fakes of dubious content and various colors were thrown in, aimed at all sections of the population and, first of all, young people. Fakes that blackmail, deceive, bribe. Russian state does not spare colossal sums of money (today some billion dollars) to this sphere.

Summing up, author notes (1) that *Russia, as an empire, has not yet passed its historical development circle, which all other states have passed through, being imperial.* And in this area, it lags far behind the world's leading powers. According to our assumption, the Russian Empire was delayed in its development by about 100 years and significantly lagged behind its former imperial counterparts of the 19th century. The empire of Muscovy approached its last stage of existence: either development or collapse, and this is confirmed when you compare the components of the formation and the reasons for the fall of empires.

Ukraine is called to accelerate this last stage of collapse (2). This is also proved by the shameful for the 21st century situation that has developed in the Russian Empire with the level of civilization of the population, with the social conditions of life, education, the spread of literacy, a very low coefficient of the intellectual level of the younger generation, mostly backward, illiterate and underdeveloped population, which it is immediately apparent from familiarity with the widespread statements and comments of ordinary Russian residents that even now they live by the ideas of the Soviet Stalinist and even monarchical times.

Even in the rare objective information of the hostile media about the state of life in the Russian outlying lands, you will not find many educated people. Russia is a country where people's brains are flooded with the cheapest vodka substitute, and where people do not see edible products for months and go hundreds of kilometers to feed their children; where schools are closed because there are no children or no teachers. Where the situation with the health care system is terrible and the rate of oligophrenicism among those born is increasing. In a country where such soldiers grew up, they drag absolutely everything from burned and looted Ukrainian houses - even frying pans, sheets, pillowcases and pillows, etc. Such information leads to desperate thoughts about the existence of a million-thousand layer of uncivilized, poor people near our border.

And this innumerable mass of people blindly trusts to the tsar-president, although he threw them at our Ukrainian cannons. Such sacrifice for the sake of the tsar, the system of upbringing and limited education

(but unlimited education is not affordable!) were implemented for decades in Russia with one goal - to easier to control the uneducated masses, which we can see on the example of today's Moscow state.

So, this imperial scheme of the Moxsel country must be purified, go through the entire path of political, economic and social development, so that a civilized civil society will be formed in its bowels, democratic forces mature, ready to challenge the ruling oligarchy. This imperial machine has to go this way (3), survive everything, finally break down to break up into numerous components. Then its outskirts will speak with their own voices and form civilized, civil societies.

Thus, the phenomenon of the "rescue" of the Russian Empire consists in the fact that the restoration and rescue of the metropolis - the conqueror and the destroyer, the exploiter and the assimilator, was carried out by its vassals - the conquered peoples. *This phenomenon is reminiscent of the Scandinavian syndrome, when victims begin to protect and save their tormentor, who has committed irreparable evil against them.*

The study of the system of construction and organization of the modern Russian empire is designed to form an adequate policy of Ukraine in relation to the Russian aggressor and identify the weaknesses of the aggressor, which will contribute to the creation of future scenarios of events and the implementation of appropriate steps around the current situation.

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